

IMPROVEMENT OF THE SPECIAL MAINTENANCE OF THE PENSION PROVISION

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Annotation: The article scientifically investigates the legal problems of pension provision for military personnel and develops proposals for improving the pension system of military personnel.

Key words: social protection, pension payments, seniority pension, disability pension, survivor's pension.

Pension provision is one of the main types of state social security for military personnel, the word "pension" comes from the Latin word "pensio" [1]. Its literal meaning is "payment" and is one of the main sources of income for a person who has reached military age, has reached old age or has been dismissed for health reasons, or who has died (deceased) in the service and his family.

In fact, if you take a quick look at the history of pensions, state-level military pensions were first introduced in the Roman Empire by Gaius Julius Caesar. Zakat has been paid in Muslim lands since the 7th century during the reign of Caliph Umar. The first pensions in Russia under Peter I were originally given only to naval officers. Later, after the October Revolution, the issue of state pensions in Turkestan began to attract legal attention. According to the Regulations on Pensions, first adopted on October 31, 1918, and the Order of the Turkestan Central Executive Committee No. 165 of January 3, 1920, 1.5 times higher than the average earnings of disabled people of the 1st group, 2 times higher than the average earnings of disabled people of the 2nd group were paid 75% of the average wage, disabled people of the 4th group were paid in the amount of 50% of the average wage [2].

On July 14, 1956, the Supreme Soviet of the former Soviet Union adopted the Law on State Pensions. Under this law, workers and military personnel, along with the disabled, were entitled to a state pension. According to lawyer A. Inoyatov, all these persons have been assigned preferential old-age pensions.

Under the 1956 law, military personnel enjoyed the same right to three categories of pensions as citizens.

With the enactment of the Servicemen's Pension Law on April 28, 1990, it used the concept of seniority and introduced a seniority pension instead of an old-age pension. This situation gave rise to new concepts in science.

For example, according to A. Inoyatov, the period of military and other special civil service, as well as the period of service in some areas, is referred to in the legislation as length of service, and in some regulations this activity is also referred to as length of service.

Lawyer Tursunov Yu. states that "citizens employed in certain types of public service, as well as in cases provided for by law, in the case of holding a certain position or a certain type of activity, may be the basis for obtaining additional benefits in addition to seniority." This period is called seniority.

Although the concepts of "long-term pension" and "old-age pension" are used in the legal literature next to each other, their differences are not disclosed.

For example, in order to receive an old-age pension on a general basis, men with 25 years of service and an age category of 60 years are not eligible for military service. This is due to the nature of military service (for example, there is an age limit for military service, there are terms of service equal to 3 days a day), high combat readiness, physiological training, excitement and other circumstances do not allow serving 42 years before retirement is not an easy task.

Therefore, when talking about the provision of pensions for servicemen, the pension for long service is considered first of all.

In particular, A. Inoyatov said that "a seniority pension is a pension determined, as a rule, by a certain level of special service, regardless of age and actual ability to work, which aims to save such citizens from the need to continue working for years on covering a significant part of the wages that they lost due to a transfer to another job or the complete termination of their employment relationship.

Taking into account these features, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Pensions of Citizens" states that in addition to state pensions for old age, disability and loss of a breadwinner, Article 5 of the law also provides for the conditions, norms and procedure for providing pensions to prosecutors in rank (military ranks), as well as members of their families is established by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "They are also entitled to receive a pension on the grounds provided for by this law. At the same time, all types of remuneration are taken into account in the same way as the salaries of citizen-military personnel, heads of internal affairs bodies and ordinary employees, employees of judges and prosecutors with higher ranks (military ranks)" [5].

Uzbekistan has developed a modern legal framework for providing pensions to employees of the judiciary, the prosecutor's office or law enforcement agencies.

But our legislation on military pensions is lagging behind the reform process.

In particular, an independent modern national law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on pension provision has not yet been adopted.

Although the old law of 1990 is still in force, many of its provisions do not meet the requirements of the times, and some of the provisions do not work.

For example, according to Article 46 of the Law, the calculation of the average salary for calculating pensions is carried out in accordance with Article 31 of the Law "On State Pensions" and in the manner prescribed by the Cabinet of Ministers. However, the procedure for calculating the individual salary coefficient approved by the Cabinet of Ministers does not correspond to the current procedure for calculating military pensions.

Many provisions of the former USSR law of 1990 create difficulties in law enforcement practice. There is a huge "portfolio" of regulations that ensure compliance with current standards. In our opinion, military pensions can only be improved through the adoption of a new modern law. To this end, the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan has prepared a draft law "On state pensions for persons who have completed military service, served in law enforcement and customs agencies, and members of their families." The project was launched in 2021 on the portal for discussing the regulatory documents of Uzbekistan - "Projekt.gov.uz".

This law is one of the first steps towards improving the military pension legislation, and we believe that it will serve as a solid basis for improving military pensions in the near future.

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